

Your search parameters were adjusted to search for a short input sequence.
 Your results are filtered to match records that include: Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Rv (taxid:83332)

Job Title [mpt64 malditof ...](#)
 RID [70FMXFRJ013](#) Search expires on 05-27 13:07 pm
 Program BLASTP
 Database nr
 Query ID lc|Query_72317
 Description [unnamed protein product ...](#)
 Molecule type amino acid
 Query Length 16

Compare these results against the new Clustered nr database

Descriptions

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
immunoprotective protein Mpt64 [Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex]	Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex	57.1	57.1	100%	7e-08	100.00%	228	WP_003409954.1

Graphic Summary

Distribution of the top 1 Blast Hits on 1 subject sequences

Alignments

Alignment view CDS feature

MULTISPECIES: immunoprotective protein Mpt64 [Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex]

Sequence ID: [WP_003409954.1](#) Length: 228 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 1 to 16

Score	Expect	Identities	Positives	Gaps	Frame
57.1 bits(127)	7e-08()	16/16(100%)	16/16(100%)	0/16(0%)	
Query 1	MRIKIFMLVTAVVLLC	16			
Sbjct 1	MRIKIFMLVTAVVLLC	16			

Taxonomy

Reports

Lineage

Organism	Blast Name	Score	Number of Hits	Description
Mycobacterium	high G+C Gram-positive bacteria		3	
.Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex	high G+C Gram-positive bacteria	57.1	1	Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex hits
.Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Rv	high G+C Gram-positive bacteria	57.1	2	Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Rv hits

- **Organism**

Description	Score	E value	Accession
Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex [high G+C Gram-positive bacteria]			
MULTISPECIES: immunoprotective protein Mpt64 [Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex]	57.1	7e-08	WP_003409954
Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Rv [high G+C Gram-positive bacteria]			
immunogenic protein Mpt64 [Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Rv]	57.1	7e-08	NP_216496
RecName: Full=Immunogenic protein MPT64; AltName: Full=Antigen MPT64; Flags: Precursor [Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Rv]	57.1	7e-08	P9WIN9

- **Taxonomy**

Taxonomy	Number of hits	Number of Organisms	Description
Mycobacterium	3	2	
. Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex	1	2	Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex hits
.. Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Rv	2	1	Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Rv hits